

Aspects of Diaspora Reflected in the Writings of Jhumpa Lahiri and Rohinton Mistry: An Overview

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Abstract

In the present paper attempts will be made to define the term 'Diaspora', etymology of the term Diaspora, a very brief history of the word diaspora and its reflection in the select works of Jhumpa Lahiri and Rohinton Mistry.

The word "diaspora" is being used very extensively in many of the fields including journalistic writing, political and academic discourses taking the themes of migration and cultural, emotional and other walks of life of the immigrated people from one country to the other. 'In the twentieth century, the meaning of the term gradually expanded to cover the involuntary dispersal of other populations, especially Armenians and people of African descent since the 1980s diaspora has proliferated to a remarkable extent, to the point where it is now applied to migrants of almost every kind'(Kevin,1). In the beginning, it would be used in the context of Jew dispersal and exile, but later it very commonly used in other fields. The Greek noun *diaspora* derives from the verb *diaspeirein* a compound of "dia"(over or through) and "speirein" (to scatter or sow) The word emerged from the proto-Indo- European root *spr* , which can be found today in such English words as "spere", "sperm", "spread" and "disperse". In all of its various uses, diaspora has something to do with scattering and dispersal. To the ancient Greeks, diaspora seems to have signified mainly a process of destruction. (2) However, diaspora and the Jewish History have a very close connection. Later, the term diaspora was connected theology. The Jews, according to the Bible disobeyed God's law, therefore, as a punishment they were exiled and their only hope was 'repentance'.

Introduction-

As far as the extraordinary proliferation of the term 'diaspora' is concerned, it extended its wings in the academic domain since the 1980s covering all sorts of immigration. However, historical development is also responsible for its spread. Novel technological as well as communicational means could provide impetus to the international immigration in the recent past. The field of diaspora studies now has its own special centres and journals. Khachig To'lo'lyan, a Syrian- born professor of English at Wesleyan University, whose Armenian parents moved to the United States by way of Syria, Lebanon, and Egypt, has edited *Diaspora: Studies*, published in New Delhi, focuses on Indian migration, while *South Asian Diaspora* based in the United Kingdom, covers migration from and within the subcontinent (10). The widespread of the term 'diaspora' shows very patently that something has been stored in the minds and that began to come out in terms of writing.

Defining 'diaspora' seems to be very difficult and inconsistent as the term embraces many elements of society. Jewish captivity, African Slavery, Armenian

genocide and the Irish famine, etc cannot be counted as a one single entity; rather many elements are involved into it. Migration of merchants, workers, and colonizers cannot be considered as a one single purpose. As a result of this a coherent definition of the term 'diaspora' seems impossible; however, some criteria can be clubbed together and can be defined. Again, the problem remains unresolved as which of the criteria are fit and which are unfit for the term. One more thing has to be noted here that the word 'diaspora' has become a synonym for population movements in general, not just compulsory migration. Thus, a single and well knit definition of the term diaspora is simply not feasible.

Jhumpa Lahiri

Jhumpa Lahiri wrote some novels and collections of short stories bringing into them diasporic elements in them. Her debut and Pulitzer Prize winning short collection *Interpreter of Maladies* narrates the intensity of diasporic emotions in terms of diverse characters portrayed in the stories. She brought out the post-colonial and post-modern impact on the lives of immigrants with the help of her writings. Jhumpa Lahiri, being an American writer, brought to light

American experiences of Indians and Indian experiences to an American. Her story "A Temporary Matter" narrates the life of an Indian couple in a foreign land. The protagonists of the story suffer manage the familial bondage. The protagonist of the story Shoba has been portrayed as an individual having her self-identity. She is an example of a modern woman having the capabilities of self-decision. The protagonist Shukumar expresses and shows his respect for Shoba's nature, however, gradual detachment is found between the couple taking Shoba's self-reliant nature. The death of their new born baby brought a kind of chasm in their relations and began to lead a life of seclusion from each other. At the end of the story it has been found that immigrant life could become an obstacle in cordial relationship even in the country like India.

Her stories like, "When Mr Pirzada Came to Dine", "A Real Durwan", "The Treatment of Bibi Haldar", etc revolves around the diasporic elements showing alienation and detachment. All in all, the stories of Jhumpa Lahiri have been considered to be the scrutiny of various dimensions of diaspora commencing from the inner self to the outer circle. Her stories, besides analyzing this factor, they also focus on the diaspora of time and community.

Rohinton Mistry

Rohinton Mistry, an Indian born Canadian writer is a recipient of many prestigious awards including Neustadt International Prize for Literature in 2012. He wrote books such as- *A Fine Balance*, *Such a Long Journey*, *Family Matters*, *Tale from Firozsha Baag*, *Swimming Lessons* and *The Scream* etc.

Rohinton Mistry expressed his views pertaining to the clash between the old culture of India and the new culture of Canada in terms of his writings. One can find his intention about description of trans-cultural space in his novels. Home land and

host land conflict is being observed through his fictional work. His novels *Such a Long Journey* and *A Fine Balance* are the excellent examples of diaspora writing. The novel *Such a Long Journey* brings out the historical events as its setting and background, and the inward journey of the major characters, residing in the Khodabad building. In this novel the writer employs images and symbols more decisively for the reconstruction of past memories.

A Fine Balance brings out a number of paradoxical situations, where the reader is emotionally moved by. In the novel the writer very keenly depicts the history with invincibility of human mind. The characters retain a collective memory, vision and myth of their marginalized group – its trauma, suffering and struggle collectively share the efforts of balancing their lives in their different specific way.

To conclude, Jhumpa Lahiri and Rohinton Mistry very patently and minutely portrayed the aspects of diaspora in terms of their writings. Self-alienation, loss of identity, quest for identity, cultural mutation, familial detachment, etc is the central and integral part of their writing. I could not extensively deal with the characterization and themes of every individual work due to space constraints.

Works Cited

- 1) Dodiya, Jaydipsinh. *The Fiction of Rohinton Mistry: Critical Studies* New Delhi: Prestige Books, 1998.
- 2) Kenny, Kevin. *Diaspora A Very Short Introduction*, Oxford University Press, New York, 2013 p 1
- 3) ----- p. 2
- 4) -----p. 10
- 5) Lahiri, Jhumpa. "Interpreter of Maladies". Harper Collins Publisher, 1999, UK